

**Name Games: Paul Klee's Titling as Self-Referential Practice
(Developed from 2023 Princeton BA Thesis, "The Bookkeeper-Magician")**

Annabelle B. Berghof

The BA Thesis was Submitted to the Department of Art and Archaeology, Princeton University,
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Bachelor of Arts Princeton, New
Jersey

Zwitscher-Maschine.org No.15 / 2024 Supplement / Version 2, 4.11.2024

Introduction

In the basement of the Rosengart Collection in Lucerne, Switzerland, is a renowned collection of works by Paul Klee. A small watercolor mounted on a cream-colored piece of paperboard hangs with other images from different periods in the artist's career (Figure 1). A curtain painted on its left side invites the viewer into the watercolor's murky background, which is inhabited by a spindly figure with rounding, connected spirals for eyes, and a head that seems to unravel into billowing gossamer in the darkness. The ghostly creature holds its hands up to its head in an anxious gesture reminiscent of figures in cave paintings. This inscrutable pose is part of a performance whose script was forever lost.

When one looks for a wall label to tell them more about this mysterious image, they will not see the same standard museum placards that were paired with each Picasso work upstairs. At the bottom of the painting, though, the viewer's attention would eventually fall on an unassuming line with *1922/87* inscribed to the left and *Ausschnitt aus einem Ballett zur Aeolsharfe* on the right. The title means "Excerpt from a Ballet on the Aeolian Harp," suggesting that the figure is being blown by a gale. The watercolor transforms into a visual pun: the German word *Ausschnitt* designates "excerpt," or "detail," but it can be translated literally as "cutout." Klee was punning on the cut appearance of the right side of the watercolor, shearing another unlucky dancer in half. The term would be appropriate to use for a small portion of a work on paper or an excerpt from a film, but not for the medium of live performance. Somehow, though, the title's farce does not diminish the mysterious pathos evoked by the first ballet dancer's appearance.

Paul Klee could craft poignant fantasies that seemed related to the oldest of myths, and he did it with an airy musicality and an unmatched wit. A voracious reader, Klee had struggled to

choose between the professions of painter and poet. Ultimately, he did not need to choose, as he nimbly reconciled these disciplines in the vast oeuvre he produced over the course of his life.² Klee's textually rich creations gained him major international recognition by critics and the public during and after his lifetime, even in the 1950s and 60s when the inclusion of literary references in painting came to be seen as anathema to its supposed aim of achieving medium-specific purity.³ The artist's own works formed a muse for the poetry of his titles. Studying Klee's art makes clear that the reverse was also true – his titles could become integrated with visual elements within his images. Klee was not only a magician who could bring fantastical stories to life, but an organizing enthusiast for whom a label could become a phenomenologically rich work of art.⁴

Klee's titling practice constituted a multifaceted part of his creative activity with a decisive influence on the artist's unique combinations of words and images. For Klee, the artwork's marginalia could become a constituent part of the work of art, itself.⁵ A title could enter the pictorial field, and Klee's choice of title could prompt the artist to make changes in a work. Klee did not speak much about his titling process, with his longest description of it encompassing a few sentences in a lecture he delivered to the Jena *Kunstverein* in 1924. After the artist had balanced formal elements like line, tonal value, and color, his creation might prompt mental "associations" with objects in the world. While Klee derided this process when it resulted in a banal recollection of what was familiar to a viewer, he acknowledged the

² Klee humorously considers these three choices in a diary entry: "Music, for me, is a love bewitched. Fame as a painter? Writer, modern poet? Bad joke. So I have no calling, and loaf." 1964 Diary I Munich; First Year of Study 1898-1899, 26.

³ See Clement Greenberg 1940 On Greenberg's praise of Klee's problematization of the "purely plastic" and the "literary," See Bourneuf 2015, S. 4

⁴ Inspiration for my use of "magician" is from Hausenstein 1921, S. 6

⁵ Jenny Anger has influenced my thought as far as Klee including elements in the work that are thought external to it in *Paul Klee and the Decorative in Modern Art* (Cambridge, 2004), as has Annie Bourneuf's elucidation of Klee incorporating literature into the work of art in *Paul Klee: The Visible and the Legible* (Chicago, 2015).

productivity of associative thought for the title of a work when the artist attended to the specific character of elements within his image:

With the gradual growth of such an image before the eyes an association of ideas gradually insinuates itself which may tempt one to a material interpretation. For any image of complex structure can, with some effort of imagination, be compared with familiar pictures from nature.

These associative properties of the structure, once exposed and labelled, no longer correspond wholly to the direct will of the artist (at least not to his most intensive will) and just these associative properties have been the source of passionate misunderstandings between artist and layman....

But sooner or later, the association of ideas may itself occur to him, without the intervention of a layman. Nothing need then prevent him from accepting it, provided that it introduces itself under its proper title.

Acceptance of this material association may suggest additions which, once the subject is formulated, clearly stand in essential relationship to it. If the artist is fortunate, these natural forms may fit into a slight gap in the formal composition, as though they had always belonged there.

The argument is therefore concerned less with the question of the existence of an object, than with its appearance at any given moment – with its nature.

I only hope that the layman, who in a picture, always looks for his favourite subject, will, as far as I am concerned, gradually die out and remain to me nothing but a ghost which cannot help its failings. For a man only knows his objective passions. And admittedly it gives him great pleasure when, by chance, a familiar face of its own accord emerges from a picture.

The objects in pictures look out at us serene or severe, tense or relaxed, comforting or forbidding, suffering or smiling.⁶

Klee compared his titling activity with a kind of viewership characteristic of a layman who was unfamiliar with the nature of the artist's practice, which proceeded in a manner akin to natural growth processes but was not intended to reproduce nature. Although Klee attacked the lay viewer for being more prone to shutting down the image's power to generate new ideas, so

⁶ Klee 1966

long as these “material associations” were productive ones, Klee evidently did not care much about with whom they originated. Indeed, Klee was known to have allowed his friends and students to title his works.⁷ For Klee, the titling process was a dynamic part of the work of art’s conception and reception that also sometimes affected its development. Just as he maintained productive tensions between image and text in his work, so did Klee find a way to integrate a work of art with its paratext, the title, which he generally listed in his personal catalogue and inscribed on the object’s paperboard mount.

Klee’s titling of his work seems to have begun partly for the same economic purpose as the overall practice of giving works of art specific titles, which first became a common practice in the Netherlands in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.⁸ In 1911, towards the beginning of his career, Klee began to keep notebooks fastidiously filled with lists of entries for his works.⁹ Entries in these notebooks consisted of some combination of a reference number, a work’s title, its medium, ground, and occasionally also its dimensions. Klee initially used the catalogue primarily to facilitate the sale and display of his works. It was likely a private sales document akin to a business ledger, as Klee began keeping the catalogue following his first solo exhibition in Switzerland in 1910/11.¹⁰ Klee stated in 1911:

All the things an artist must be: poet, explorer of nature, philosopher! And now I have become a bureaucrat as well by compiling a large, precise catalogue [*Verzeichnis*] of all my artistic productions [*Produkte*] since my childhood. I have left out only the school drawings, studies of nudes, etc., because they lack productive self-sufficiency.¹¹

⁷ Kröll 1968

⁸ Yeazell 2016, S. 25

⁹ Sladeczek 2000, S. 146

¹⁰ Okuda 1997, S. 376

¹¹ Klee, *Diaries*, “Diary III,” 256, No. 895. German from Paul Klee, *Tagebücher von Paul Klee, 1898-1918* (Köln: M. DuMont Schauberg, 1957), 255.

Klee's descriptions of himself as a "bureaucrat" and his works of art as "products" convey that he viewed his catalogue as a tool he could use as if he was his own dealer, a practice whose worldliness he humorously contrasted with the more detached intellectual pursuits expected of modern artists.

Klee's entries from 1911 to 1921 reflect this economic usage of the catalogue, listing prices and names of buyers for his works. In 1911, Klee was selling his works under a contract with the Munich dealer Hans Goltz, hence the frequent stampings of "*verkauft Goltz*," or "sold Goltz" on his catalogue's pages.¹² Several of Klee's contemporaries also created similar private catalogues of their own works in the 1910s to ostensibly economic ends. One was Emil Nolde, a member of the Dresden-based Expressionist group *Die Brücke*, and another was Wassily Kandinsky, Klee's lifelong friend and Bauhaus colleague whom he met around 1911.¹³ Like Klee, Nolde and Kandinsky first used the catalogue as an instrument for retaining information related to the sales of their works, listing prices for each composition.¹⁵¹⁶ Additionally, none of the artists seem to have intended their catalogues for public use: all remained unpublished during their respective lifetimes.¹⁷

The catalogue was only one half of Klee's titling practice, however. Klee displayed his titles to his viewers by copying varying degrees of information in his catalogue entries onto the paperboard mounts he made for his works. These labels likely helped their maker to keep track of works in his possession, but also allowed him a greater degree of control over how his

¹² Sladeczek 2000, S. 151

¹³ Klee 1962, S. 35–48

¹⁴ Sladeczek mentions these artists in "Der handschriftliche Œuvre-Katalog von Paul Klee," 157–58.

¹⁵ Röthel/Kandinsky/Benjamin 1982, S. 17

¹⁶ Urban/Nolde 1987, S. 37

¹⁷ In the 1930s, Nolde did create a more formalized catalogue that he intended for publication. However, his catalogues from the first decade of the twentieth century, like Kandinsky's and Klee's, remained unpublished in his lifetime. Urban/Nolde 1987, S. 39

compositions would be viewed and interpreted. Klee's mounts formed a direct connection between artist and his present viewers like those at the gallery *Der Sturm* in Berlin.¹⁸ Even in the present, the curators of the Rosengart have opted to allow Klee's inscriptions to take the place of wall labels, like those that accompany Picasso's works upstairs. Beyond the grave, Klee is allowed to be a curator for his own work.

The first scholar to pay substantive attention to Klee's interconnected catalogues and mounts focused on how the artist implemented them to steer his reception among his present public. In the 1980s, Marxist art historian Otto Karl Werckmeister applied Adorno's critique of ideology in works of art and media to Klee's early oeuvre.¹⁹ In seeking to demonstrate how Klee had been a shrewd publicist for his own work and not always the detached mystic that the artist sometimes made himself out to be, Werckmeister showed how Klee changed titles of works in his catalogue and on his mounts when they were exhibited at galleries like *Der Sturm* in 1916.²⁰ Werckmeister's study has received criticism for its one-sidedly negative view of artistic production under capitalism, eliminating any possibility for political subversiveness in Klee's work. However, it did illuminate how Klee penciled in "provisional titles" early in his career that he could change in advance of exhibitions.²¹

However, just as one cannot explain all the features of Klee's work by pointing to the demands of his buyers, so one cannot account for the role of the artist's catalogue and paperboard supports in his creative practice with the same move. After around 1921, it is evident that Klee's catalogue was serving a different purpose from a purely economic one. Klee's

¹⁸ Anger lists the exhibitions in which Klee took part in the latter half of the 1910s, the period Werckmeister discusses. See Anger 2004, S. 214–216

¹⁹ Otto Karl Werckmeister, *The Making of Paul Klee's Career, 1914-1920* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1989), 9.

²⁰ Werckmeister 1989, S. 73

²¹ See Craven 1990

groupings of works in exhibitions stopped in 1919, at around the same time as the attachments of prices.²² The artist's catalogue beginning in this period could be a creative tool in addition to a bookkeeping device, helping to integrate the act of naming into the work of art.

Klee's labels could allow a painting to transform into a reflection on its periphery, as in 1928's *Fenced in* (1928, 74). In this composition, Klee painted over his mount and then reframed the resulting image to create a *trompe l'oeil* presenting the mount as part of a painting. Klee was evidently not only interested in labeling as a record-keeping practice but also as a chance to play with the ideas that it signified. One of these notions was that of an impassable boundary delimiting the work of art's "finish." Works like *Fenced in* show us that we need to look further than Klee's initial statements about titling to begin to see what other uses he might have had for it. The title was clearly part of Klee's creative practice in a way that was not always directly connected to his consideration of imminent gallery exhibition. How the artist used his multifaceted creative tool varied over the course of his career—he tested its potential uses like the wide variety of mediums he used to create his compositions.

This practice can be understood within a larger set of issues around writing that were central to the artist's work. In the late 1910s and early 1920s, Klee began to include letters and phrases in his compositions. Drawing connections between writing and drawing, as well as reading and viewing, were key ideas for Klee, as Annie Bourneuf has shown in her study of the juncture of the visual and the verbal in his practice during this period. Bourneuf and a host of other art historians, especially K. Porter Aichele, have extensively discussed the way Klee's art engages with questions related to language and writing.²³ Porter Aichele and Bourneuf were not

²² Sladeczek 2000, S. 151

²³ A selection of some significant literature on Klee and language: K. Porter Aichele, *Paul Klee's Pictorial Writing* (Cambridge, U.K. ; New York : Cambridge University Press, 2002), Annie Bourneuf, *Paul Klee: The Visible and the*

primarily focused on Klee's titles, although they do both pay close attention to his titles' contributions to interpretations of individual works that they analyze. Bourneuf and Porter Aichele's treatments of Klee's titles, as well as Charles W. Haxthausen's in his writing on Klee's late work, inform the analysis of formal features in art objects within the present study of the interaction between title and image.

Klee's christening of an image with a title was a dynamic and often self-referential mental process of "association" that changed throughout the artist's career and has a crucial bearing on many works' content. Focusing on works created at two significant points in the artist's career lends insight into continuity and difference across his varied titling practice. The first era is Klee's service in the First World War and its immediate aftermath, and the second is the year 1939, when Klee produced the most art he had in a single year despite his advanced case of scleroderma in exile. Close readings of *E (fragmentary Watercolor)* (1918, 199), a watercolor whose revised title on its mount Klee changed in a manner that mirrors the appearance of the composition, as well as the drawings in the series *der Inferner Park (The Inferner Park)* (1939, 238-253), one among multiple instances of image categorization in the artist's late titling practice, reveal that the titles of these works embed allusions to Klee's processes of creating the compositions. Borrowing from psychoanalysis and structuralist literary theory, I show that Klee's methods of titling not only changed throughout his career, but also constituted creative acts that could clarify or expand the claims any given work made about its own genesis.

Klee's titles are notable in the history of modernism for their idiosyncrasy, not fitting neatly into any of the three main categories of title that John C. Welchman identifies in his history of modern titles in the visual arts: "denotative titles," in which words describe elements

Legible (Chicago, 2015), Albert Cook, "The Sign in Klee," *Word & Image* 2, no. 4 (October 1, 1986): 363–81, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02666286.1986.10435360>, and Vogel 1992

in the image or their external referents, “connotative” titles, which introduce ideas or images not derivable from its visual form, alone, and “systematic, non-referential designations” such as the convention of naming an image “Untitled.”²⁴ Although closest to the second type of title in content, Klee’s inscriptions seem to occupy a space between the excess of connotation often present in Surrealist titles and the terse matter-of-factness in Kandinsky’s serial categories. In form, Klee’s titles are reminiscent of Max Ernst’s labels for his collages that similarly echo illustration captions or explanations of scientific diagrams, but Klee’s are visually distinct in their occasional mimicry of elements in a drawing or painting.

There has been some critical literature specifically on the topic of Klee’s titles, though certainly not so vast as that which has been dedicated to the appearance of writing and writing-like signs within his compositions. In 1980, for the first of the Guggenheim Museum’s Hilla Rebay Lectures, Ernst Gombrich took as his subject “Image and Word in Twentieth-Century Art” and set out to describe key developments in titles of Modern Art through the lens of mental “fit” theories in psychology.²⁵ The talk, which was later published as an article in the third issue of the journal *Word and Image* in 1985, singled out Klee’s titles as exceptional in the history of modern art. Gombrich created the moniker “Aha Titles” for them: “What are we to make of these curves and these half realised heads? Oh! of course, it is a *Peach harvest* (1937, Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum, New York). Psychologists speak of the 'Aha' experience, oh yes, of course, that is it; I suggest that Klee's titles belong to the unique category of Aha Titles.”²⁶ *Ausschnitt aus einem Ballett zur Aeolsharfe* (1922/87) at the Rosengart attests to this kind of response that can be provoked by Klee’s titles. After reading the inscription, something clicks in

²⁴ Welchman 1997, S. 8

²⁵ Gombrich 1985

²⁶ Gombrich 1985, S. 232

the viewer's mind and one feels as though a puzzle has been solved, that what they are looking at is a *Gestalt* that is now more than the sum of its parts. Gombrich's application of perceptual psychology to Klee's titles provides a good basis for further work on the mental aspect of these "associations," which became particularly salient theme in some of Klee's titles in the late 1910s and early 1920s such as *Teppich der Erinnerung*, or *Carpet of Memory* (1914, 193).²⁷

Christina Kröll's 1968 dissertation, *Die Bildtitel Paul Klees. Eine Studie Zur Beziehung von Bild Und Sprache in Der Kunst Des Zwanzigsten Jahrhunderts*, offers by far the most expansive work done on the subject, clarifying important historical precedents for Klee's titling practice while highlighting its singularity in the history of art until the mid-twentieth century.²⁸ Although her formal analyses of individual works by Klee and their relationships to their titles remain convincing, the field of Klee studies has progressed significantly since 1968, specifically regarding the artist's various reuses and alterations of his own oeuvre.²⁹ Several articles and books have focused on this issue, such as the aforementioned monograph by Otto Karl Werckmeister on Klee's management of his art and public image to suit the desires of potential buyers. Osamu Okuda's research on Klee's revision and reworking practices between 1919 and 1923 has also been groundbreaking for newer Klee research.³⁰ Retitling plays a significant part in both investigations. This new direction in Klee studies signals a need for more work on the processual form and content of his titles. Klee formed titles referencing the processes he used to create the works to which they are attached. Close readings of two titles, one designating a

²⁷ The work was formerly titled <*architektur Intérieur*>. Before Klee exhibited the oil painting in its current form in a 1922 exhibition in Wiesbaden, however, he cut <*architektur Intérieur*> off its support and rotated it ninety degrees before painting on it further. Between 1920 and 1923, Klee remounted the work and retitled it *Carpet of Memory* in the first of two oeuvre catalogues he was keeping at the time, changing the labels "long" and "wide" in the dimensions section of the listing to reflect the altered orientation. The year recorded in the catalogue does not reflect this change. See Okuda 2000

²⁸ Kröll 1968

²⁹ See, for example, Rümelin 2001; Trodd 2007

³⁰ Okuda 2000

series of fifteen drawings, reveals how the work of art and its reception became a part of these images' content.

Part 1: A Label Reflects on Itself

Klee looked to many sources for inspiration, including natural specimens and compositions by artists he admired such as Dürer and Daumier.³¹ Another body of material to which Klee turned in search of fuel for his creations was his own previous works. His oeuvre is punctuated with instances of a style, compositional element, title, material, or a combination of these re-emerging in a startlingly similar form years after Klee had originally used it.³² Klee's "recollection" of earlier works via these interconnected mediums had implications for the interpretation of his oeuvre's general stylistic features. In his influential 1954 monograph on Klee, Will Grohmann noted that the development of Klee's styles was cyclical rather than linear, and Osamu Okuda has connected this aspect of the artist's oeuvre to evidence that he actually did return to earlier compositions for their material.³³ Okuda identifies 1919-1923 as a period in which Klee's revision of earlier works was especially pronounced, pointing to multiple instances of Klee taking earlier oil paintings like *Carpet of Memory* (1914, 193) or *The God of the Northern Forest* (1922, 32) and substantially reworking them through rotation and repainting.³⁴ Such works present interesting interpretive challenges that scholars like Charles Haxthausen and Annie Bourneuf have begun to address following Okuda's discoveries. I argue that the analysis of certain images in this period should take account of the possibility that Klee's altered titles could have helped refine and shape the compositions' phenomenological and epistemological content.

³¹ Okuda 2003

³² For example, from 1922 (1922, 193) to 1925 (1925, 184) to 1937 (1937, 135), Klee repeated similar compositional elements – a lying figure and/or a torment figured by arrows - in works all given the title *Katastrophe*, or "Catastrophe."

³³ Okuda 2000, S. 159 Citing Grohmann 1935 Paul Klee, *Vortrag anlässlich der Eröffnung der Ausstellung Prof. Paul Klee*, 22. February 1935 [Kunsthalle Bern] unpublished manuscript, (copy in the Paul Klee Foundation Bern), p 6.

³⁴ Okuda 2000, S. 162–165

In 1920-23, Klee returned to earlier creations and thereby greeted the possibility of reconceptualizing a work of art. In the period immediately following the First World War, the mental apparatus of his “associations” helped the artist make these re-engagements and allowed him to transform images into visions of mental processes. His catalogue and mounts provided a framework with which Klee could imagine his compositions as memories and thoughts. An awareness of Freud’s theory of unconscious associative thought in his *Traumdeutung* (*Interpretation of Dreams*) (1899) and theories of language in German Romanticism reveals how Klee reflected the work of art and its title as an extension of his mind. The mount title of *E* (*fragmentary Watercolor*) (1918, 199) creates a visual association between the mounted work and its title, incorporating the mount, a space at the juncture of the visual and the verbal, into an enactment of language production that comes to challenge the divisions of art from life in addition to word from image.

E (fragmentary Watercolor)

Klee’s mounts served two primary purposes for the artist: firstly, they were structural supports for works on paper or loose pieces of canvas or jute, allowing them to be exhibited upright. Owing in part to his extensive experimentation with different materials, Klee’s works were and are often fragile, and the mounts therefore also provide a safeguard against potential tearing of a ground for a painting or drawing. Secondly, his mounts featured work numbers and titles that corresponded to oeuvre catalogue entries. Throughout his career, however, Klee’s mounts took on many more roles. Beginning in the early 1920s, Klee emphasized their shared characteristics with a frame, sometimes adding pieces of colored paper to image borders. In addition, through its idiosyncratic appearance including a line with the work number and title underneath the work, Klee’s mounts doubled as a kind of signature announcing that a given work

was created by the figure “Paul Klee.” All these aspects of the mounts were ultimately affected by their status as the site of Klee’s mental “associations.”

Although the notion of an association taking place on the mount would be interesting to discuss in connection with any of these functions of the mount, *E (fragmentary Watercolor)* (1918, 199) (Figure 2) specifically questions the idea of a frame between the work of art and its surroundings. The normative epistemological category for the frame of the work of art is the *parergon*, a Latin term derived from ancient Greek meaning “beside (*para-*) the work (*ergon*).”³⁵ Klee’s mounts and their titles fell within this category.³⁶ According to Derrida,

...the parergon stands out [*se détache*] both from the ergon (the work) and from the milieu, it stands out first of all like a figure on a ground. But it does not stand out in the same way as the work. The latter also stands out against a ground. But the parergonal frame stands out against two grounds [*fonds*], but with respect to each of these two grounds, it merges [*se fond*] into the other. With respect to the work which can serve as a ground for it, it merges into the wall, and then, gradually, into the general text. With respect to the background which the general text is, it merges into the work which stands out against the general background.³⁷

Klee’s mounts, and by extension, the titles on them, constituted such a liminal zone, never fully merging with the work of art and yet refusing to be considered wholly separate from it. Klee, like other artists in the twentieth century, blurred this boundary in a textual manner by including the same letters and phrases in the image and on its mount.

Klee made this aesthetic proposition with his titular “associations” in a manner that resonates with theories of mental processes within psychoanalysis. Klee’s interconnected oeuvre catalogue and mounts could be interpreted as a kind of mental apparatus staging this common

³⁵ Collins. For a good overview of theories of the frame, see Kemp 1995

³⁶ Jenny Anger has also applied the concept of *parergon* to Klee’s use of ornament in his work. See Anger 2004

³⁷ Derrida 1987, S. 61

formation of language.³⁸ In his theory of mental structures in the *Traumdeutung (Interpretation of Dreams)* (1899), Freud posited a dual model in which “a system in the very front of the apparatus receives the perceptual stimuli but retains no trace of them and thus has no memory, while behind it there lies a second system which transforms the momentary excitations of the first system into permanent traces.”³⁹ Klee’s mounts often mirrored the former system, being present to immediate perception and not generally bearing the “permanent traces” of title changes that are sometimes evident in his catalogues. Although the artist’s titles were largely consistent across his oeuvre catalogue and his mounts, Klee’s development of a system that involved dual titles for a single work also allowed him to experiment with the signifying possibilities that his mounts could offer. The mount title’s immediate visibility alongside the art object differentiated it from the catalogue title and opened the space of the mount to free mental association and visual experimentation.

This system itself was not set in stone for Klee, however; just as any attempt to generalize about the artist’s practice is bound to be met with counterexamples, so too is the case with his titles. As with Freud’s analyses of abnormal psychology, though, one can learn much about normal processes from analyzing exceptional cases that seem to contradict them. In one such case, *E (fragmentarisches Aquarell)* or *E (fragmentary Watercolor)* (1918, 199), the mount could become a site of a visible effacement of an earlier title, with a “memory trace” inhering underneath. This trace linked the title to the composition in both its appearance and the process Klee used to make space for it, integrating the mental with the material.

³⁸ Tamara Trodd has applied a slightly later Freudian model of the mind that he proposed in 1924 in his “Notiz über den Wunderblock” (“A Note Upon the Mystic Writing-Pad”) to Klee’s practice of keeping his drawings and reusing them to create oil-transfer compositions. See Trodd 2007

³⁹ Freud 2010, S. 540

Klee reused the gesso base coat of *fragmentary Watercolor* to efface its composition and create a fresh space for the large rust-colored E. in its center. Possibly as late as 1920-23, Klee also scratched out the former mount title (likely (*Fragment*)) with an E but left the title in its catalogue entry in the same condition as it was before the artist made the change (Figure 3).⁴⁰ Given that the work was in the possession of Paul Klee's son, Felix, from 1953 until 1990, and before that with his wife, it is unlikely that anyone but the artist himself made the change.⁴¹ An infrared scan did not show what was underneath the E in the composition (Figure 4), so we cannot be sure of exactly what Klee's work process would have been, but what can definitely be analyzed is the mount title's departure from its companion in the catalogue.

Despite a change to the mount title and likely also the composition, the catalogue title remains *fragmentary Watercolor*.⁴² Up to this point, Klee had used the word “*fragment*” or “*fragmentarisch*” chiefly to describe works that were fragmentary in their physical condition, i.e., that they had been cut from existing compositions,⁴³ or that contained what looked like fragments, or disparate pieces, of figures or other formal elements.⁴⁴ *Fragmentary Watercolor* seems to approximate this second type of image that Klee labeled as “fragment,” or “fragmentary.” The catalogue title can be interpreted as describing the overall condition of the

⁴⁰ Given the length of the word as delineated by the parentheses around it, it was not long enough to have read “*fragmentarisches Aquarell*.” Klee's titles in the catalogues and on his mounts are generally the same when they appear in both places, however, so one can guess the mount might have held an abbreviation of this title. One can make out traces of what may have been an uppercase “E,” as well as the lower portion of an “a,” the bottom loop of a “g,” and the tail of a “t” on the mount, suggesting that the original title could have read “(*Fragment*).”

⁴¹ Helfenstein/Rümelin 2004, Bd. 2

⁴² Okuda has identified multiple instances in which Klee retroactively listed works from his wartime years in 1920-23. *Fragmentary Watercolor* is possibly one of these retrospective listings, given that its catalogue and mount entries share some of their features. Like *fragmentary Watercolor*'s entry, these come appended to the end of the listings for a given year and generally include a diagonal strikethrough between the year and work number on the mount – a convention that Klee mainly used between 1920 and early 1923. Okuda, “Paul Klee: Buchhaltung, Werkbezeichnung und Werkprozess,” 379-380.

⁴³ This is the case for *Zwei Akte, ein Erwachsener (fragmentarisch) u. an dessen Hand e. Kinderakt* (1904, 7), *Klumpgeister, Wischgeister u Lichtgeister, (letztere sehr fragmentarisch)* (1908, 13), and *2 Fragmente* (1913, 63).

⁴⁴ One sees this practice in <*kl. kosmisches Fragment*> (1915, 203), and *Rinzibri, Kompos. mit Tierfragmenten*, (1916, 9). Aichele also suggests these possibilities for the catalogue title. See Aichele 2002, S. 121–122

watercolor, whose geometric forms have one of their three sides filled in and whose lines tend to terminate before forming connections with other lines. *Fragmentary Watercolor*'s purely textual form contrasts with the mount title of *E*, which visually reproduces the composition. Both the *E* in the work and that which adorns its mount are grounded on effacements of earlier forms, creating a noticeable parallel beyond the basic unity of the letter. This mirroring becomes incorporated into the associative 'thoughts' about language within the work. *E*'s title is an especially relevant example to discuss in the context of shared mental processes in the work and in its title given that the watercolor it titles takes the mental act of naming as one of its central subjects.

Where *Carpet of Memory* (1914, 193), another reworked composition from the same period, presents the act of memory formation, *E* visualizes the mental act of naming. The status of the typographical "E." is made eidetic by its allusion to an abbreviation, as K. Porter Aichele points out. She asserts that the "E." is abbreviation of "Eiffel Tower," or *Eiffelturm* in German, pointing to the influence that seeing Delaunay's paintings of the Eiffel Tower in a visit to his studio in 1912 had on Klee.⁴⁵ The "E" was certainly meant to have an ambiguous signification, but it also visually recalls the Eiffel Tower with its rigidly scaffolded construction and brown color. Porter Aichele points to the Ferris wheel-like structure that the white paint in "E" partially effaces as further evidence of this connection, given the similar positioning of a Ferris wheel relative to the Eiffel Tower in several of Delaunay's paintings. In her analysis of *E*, Porter Aichele makes use of Norman Bryson's categories of "discursive" and "figural" signs, the former being "those features which show the influence over the image of language," and the latter constituting "those features which belong to the image as a visual experience independent

⁴⁵ Aichele 2002, S. 123

of language.”⁴⁶ She categorizes the E as a triumph of the “discursive” over the “figural,” literally blocking what she assumes to have been a more figural painting of the Eiffel Tower from our view.⁴⁷ One type of sign replaces another, just as one textual sign did in the title.

The work that *E* retitled was not just concerned with replacing the figural with the discursive, as Porter Aichele suggests, but also with the activity of naming. The mounted work shows how Klee integrated the epistemological with the material through analogizing the act of naming to the application of paint on paper. As an uppercase letter with a dot next to it, the form of the E references abbreviation, generally used for proper nouns in both English and German. Both Klee’s incomplete application of white gesso on the watercolor and the similar size of the resulting white area and the E atop it suggest that the gesso was applied to create space for this abbreviated name.⁴⁸ The substance that Klee used to paint over the watercolor composition was likely the same gesso that the artist originally applied as an adherent for the watercolor paint. Just as Klee attached watercolor to the ground of the sheet of paper, so did he “attach” language to the composition. By using it to visually create space for a proper name, Klee connected the medium’s adhesive material function to the activity of giving a name to an object.

For Klee, as for Wittgenstein in his contemporaneous picture-theory of language, it was a quality of shared spatial relationships between signifier and signified that generated and constituted language.⁴⁹ The scratching-out of (*Fragment*) and its replacement with *E* takes on

⁴⁶ Bryson 1983, S. 6

⁴⁷ Aichele 2002, S. 124 Upon viewing the work in person with ZPK conservator Myriam Weber in January 2023, she noticed that the base of the Ferris Wheel-like form in the upper left of the composition which appears to be hidden by the gesso, as Porter Aichele claims, is in fact likely painted on top of the gesso. The opacity of this substance is such that “ghosts of images” would not easily show through.

⁴⁸ The material is likely gesso because Klee did not list any other materials used in the work than watercolor and gesso. Additionally supporting this conclusion is the artist’s ability to paint in watercolor over the white color, evidenced by the light blue form on the upper right (it would be much harder to get watercolor to adhere so well to oil). Substance also confirmed to likely be gesso by ZPK conservator Myriam Weber in January 2023 conversation.

⁴⁹ Wittgenstein 2009

spatial as well as semantic significance through a visual parallel with the effacement in the composition. A relationship between elements in the mount title mirrors that which occurs in the watercolor. Klee left fragmentary sections of geometric shapes visible on the sides of the gesso in the watercolor, and in a direct parallel, portions of the previous work title remain to the sides of the area that has been scratched out on the mount's title underline. This figural connection between elements shifts the emphasis from being solely on the E's discursive content to its spatial linkages with other forms present on the mount. This type of structure, evincing a particular attitude towards language, recurs in Klee's practice beginning in about 1920. The artist fashioned titles like "*a*" *abstracte* → (1920, 100) and *Station L 112, 14 km* (1920, 112) (Figure 5), whose bold typefaces are not simply the flourishes of a labeling enthusiast but reflect the relationships between themselves and other pictorial elements. These are not just any letters but *those* letters in the work of art that Klee repeats in his titles. They are not simply rewritings of letters in the images but repetitions of the hand movements Klee used in composing the letters in the pictorial field. On *E*'s mount, a similar "ground" for the work of art as the gesso, Klee extended the equivalency he drew between a material process involved in composing an image and the mental process of forming a name. Klee literally foregrounded the idea of a "mount" for something as a common ground for exchange between the normatively discursive space of the paperboard and the more pictorial realm of the artwork.

The processual element of Klee's title content was rooted in the artist's memory. Klee's effacement of pictorial elements for the sake of emphasizing a letter that appears stenciled through its clean lines recalls the artist's duties at an air base in Schleißheim, Bavaria, out of which he would have been recently transferred if we are to take Klee at his word for when this image was created (1918). Felix Klee, who owned *E* from 1953 to 1990, suggested this

explanation for the appearance of the work.⁵⁰ Felix's father described this process of painting and repainting make and model abbreviations on planes as monotonous in multiple letters to his family from the air base, yet Paul Klee found ways to incorporate remnants of such rote wartime activities into his work in this period, including airplane fabric and account tables from his bookkeeping job.⁵¹ In his title, then, Klee was going back to a moment of effacement in the work that likewise originated in his experiences during the war.

A memory of his previous artistic activity, itself grounded in a bodily memory of repeated motion, formed the basis of Klee's "association" in *E*'s title. Freud's discussion of associative thought in *The Interpretation of Dreams* is helpful in understanding this kind of repressed association: "Whenever one psychical element is linked with another by an objectionable or superficial association, there is also a legitimate and deeper link between them which is subjected to the resistance of censorship."⁵² For Freud, the "memory-trace" within the mind that prompted an unconscious association could be hidden within a mental system that stored such traces. The watercolor formerly known as (*Fragment*) and its title once likely stood in a more coherent associative relationship to one another, but Klee physically repressed this connection through a painting-over and a scratching-out, respectively. By doing so, Klee created an image-title pair incorporating a visual, potentially less conscious mental connection where a more logical one previously stood. What Klee has done here goes beyond an analogy between the physical and mental processes of composing language. Klee had already accomplished this feat in his works, alone. One must not forget that with this "association," Klee was also

⁵⁰ Klee 1984, S. 17

⁵¹ Bern

⁵² Freud 2010, S. 533

transgressing a boundary between the work of art and the outside world and thereby questioning the integrity of interiority.

This doubled relationship between title and work presents an issue for notions of the autonomy of art. In his deconstruction of Kant's definition of the *parergon*, Derrida laid out some central and, from the perspective of Kantian aesthetics, troubling notions of the frame of the work of art as a stable border between a detached realm proper to aesthetic judgment and its exterior. Namely, where does the "frame" of a work of art begin and end? Many works of art from before and after Klee's time would ask this question; Derrida cites examples of images that seem to be all frame from Kant's point of view, images that share the *mise en abyme* quality of *E*.⁵³ In an addition of titles on frames to this discussion, Klee's mount title in *E* begs the question: for an artist whose images can stand for thought processes, what differentiates the kind of mental work embodied in processes that occur in the *ergon* from the *parergon* of its mount title?

To answer this question in a work whose subject is naming approximates both composing language and a theory of what language is. Klee's conception of language in his mount title expanded upon his questioning of how language functioned within the image. Paul Klee felt that the picture plane could become a productive synthesis of letters and representational elements in ways that made claims about the genesis of language.⁵⁴ The artist had read Wilhelm Weule's *Vom Kerbstock zum Alphabet* (1915), which described possible pictorial origins of language. He subsequently included ideogram-like symbols followed by letters and then entire words in his

⁵³ Derrida 1987, S. 61

⁵⁴ Aichele 2002, S. 114

creations.⁵⁵ The E can be seen as a kind of emblem for Klee's different solutions to the question of how one titles an image that includes language, which Klee's increasingly did in the 1920s.

Klee gave different answers during this period. In the case of *E.n ten (Ducks)* (1919, 195) and *Memorial Page for Emma* (1916, 18), Klee used the title of a single letter as the full form of an abbreviation. However, when one turns to the later works in 1922 and 24, like *Gedenkblatt an E. (Memorial sheet for E)* (1924, 122) and *Landschaft bei E. (in bayern) (Landscape by E (in Bavaria))* (1921, 21), one sees that Klee had increasingly varied his titles in relation to the use of an E in his compositions. When an E appeared in a work, Klee would not always give an exposition of the sign's potential meaning but instead tended to repeat the letter in the title. In these examples, one sees suggestions for a general category the E could signify, such as the name of a location, but overall, they reprise rather than explain.

The question of how to name language in the pictorial field arose in the twentieth century with the Cubists upon their inclusion of letters within their collages. One can see Klee's use of gesso to "ground" his E on the page as being in dialogue just as much with Delaunay as with Picasso and Braque's pieces of newsprint glued onto their works within collage, itself a medium that Rosalind Krauss describes as a "metalanguage of the visual."⁵⁶ As Gombrich notes, however, Picasso often stuck to obstinately "hermetic" titles that referenced traditional genres of painting, leading the viewer to struggle to reconcile the verbal and visual cues with which they were presented. This practice, he rightly points out, could be understood as part of the artistic act.⁵⁷ For Klee, the title of a work that included pieces of text was at times mysterious regarding the meaning of said text, but it was rarely oblivious to it. Many in the dada movement often also

⁵⁵ Aichele 2002, S. 13

⁵⁶ Krauss 1981, S. 19

⁵⁷ Gombrich 1985, S. 223

made titles using text present in their collages. When one of Schwitters' collages from the beginning of the 1920s, for example, included a piece of newsprint or other printed text, its letters might similarly gravitate towards the title.⁵⁸ For both Klee and Schwitters, treating text as a found object in their work allowed them to explore its formal characteristics, and this attitude evidently carried over to their titles.⁵⁹ Yet a title on a mount still meant something different for Klee than for Schwitters within their overall artistic programs.

For one, Klee's sense of irony in his titles distinguished them from Schwitters' deadpan repetitions of text in his *Merz* collages. Klee paid particular attention to the tone of his titles, even when they only included a single letter. *Anführungszeichen*, or quotation marks, performed a similar task in *E* (which should perhaps rightfully be called "*E*") as the recurring arrows in his images accomplished. Both of these idiosyncratic forms of punctuation introduced an excess that marked Klee's productions as lacking in comparison to an implied larger unknown whole – the creator of the arrow on the one hand, and the abbreviated name beginning with "E," on the other. The quotation marks direct our attention to the lack present in the verbal or visual fields, resulting in a sense of irony that Christine Kröll identifies with German Romanticism in her analysis of Klee's titles. Jean Paul and Novalis both thought of irony in a positive sense, striving to show us the discrepancy between our world and a greater, hidden truth.⁶⁰ The meagerness of

⁵⁸ See, for example, *Mz. 150. Oskar* (1920) in the Kunstsammlung Nordrhein-Westfalen.

⁵⁹ In response to a request for the Böhmen Kunstverein's request for Schwitters to clarify certain matters relating to the translation of his titles, the artist replied: "Concerning the titles of my Merz-drawings I would point out that most of them are just labels. You can distinguish three groups: 1. Names of cities, landscapes, people; 2. Deliberately misleading titles that were clearly chosen to underscore the fact that with abstract works there can be no connection between title and work; 3. Titles derived from any of the printed letters found on the glued picture. You can translate the city names, etc., as well as the factual titles of the second group, while the titles derived from the printed letters in the drawings cannot be translated." The untranslatability of the third type of title conveys how Schwitters valued the preservation of a sense of non-fungibility in a physical printed text, resulting in a treatment of language as both form and information in these titles. K. Schwitters, "The Artist and His Titles," in *Myself and My Aims: Writings on Art and Criticism*, ed. Megan R. Luke, trans. Timothy Grundy (University of Chicago Press, 2021), 247, <https://books.google.de/books?id=dXoWEAAAQBAJ>.

⁶⁰ Kröll 1968, S. 71

the “E.” on the mount, as well as the paradox of its simultaneous encapsulation of the E above it yet inability to capture the larger letter’s vibrant monumentality, would have appealed to a Romantic sense of humor.

Romanticism was a key source for the form and content of Klee’s titles as well as their commentaries on themselves. For, as *E* shows, a title could be a repetition of an element in Klee’s images as well as an inversion of it. In *E*, the pictorial entered the discursive, robbing it of its capacity to signify. When one turns to try and interpret the content of the title, one is met with an effacement and a *mise en abyme* of language in the “Es.” With the shared erasure staged in both the work and on the mount, *E* points to an effacement that takes place in the formation of names. Klee’s work here is suggestive of ideas concerning the nature of language within German Romanticism. The title *fragmentarisches Aquarell* in *E*’s catalogue entry and likely previous title of (*Fragment*) on the mount are possibly a reference to the Romantic fragment. The fragment was a short literary/philosophical form practiced by the “Jena Romantics” (among others), an influential circle of writers and philosophers based in Jena at the cusp of the nineteenth century.⁶¹ Romanticism’s ideas about language may have joined its motifs and general mindset in shaping Klee’s self-referential titles that engaged with mental processes.⁶²

A key similarity between Klee and strands of Romantic thought was their use of self-contained symbolic language. For Klee, this came in the mount and catalogue entry for *E*, in which one sees a distinct lack of external referentiality for language. Just as Novalis, in his *Monologue*, evinced the idea that language was a system that could generate truths by reflecting on itself, so too did Klee’s effacement of any clue in the two titles as to what the “E” stands for

⁶¹ See Schlegel 1991

⁶² Jürgen Glaesemer has discussed the kinship between Klee’s worldview and that of the German Romantics in great detail, ranging from their shared sense of humor and philosophical positions toward artmaking to their musicality. Glaesemer 1987

create the possibility for creative activity.⁶³ In creating a kind of *mise en abyme* with his “Es,” as he also did in works like *"a" abstracte* → and *Station L 112, 14 km*, Klee freed language from its referentiality. The catalogue entry is no help either, as the title within it only points towards the broad classification of “Watercolor.” The “Es” are thus liberated to stand in whatever relation they want to one another, and here it is one of inversion. Each points to the other as its possible interpretant, with the aforementioned figurative quality of the “E” on the mount leading one’s eye to the “E.” on the work, and the abbreviated form of the “E.” in the work turning us back to the mount for an explanatory title. The mirroring present in “E” adds to the work something akin to Novalis’ notion of an *ordo inversus*, an inversion that turns concepts like content and form inside out in service of an intuitive truth.⁶⁴ That this inversion took place visually across the border between the work of art and its accompanying (often representational) mental “associations” strengthened *E*’s claim of the mind’s simultaneous renunciation of the world and illumination of its innermost secrets through language.

It is vital to consider the specificity of where and how Klee’s titles appear if one wants to develop a full account of their content. The visual immediacy of Klee’s titles on their mounts enabled the creation of *E* and the full elaboration of its message. Beginning in earnest during his time as a *Fabrikarbeiter* in the First World War painting abbreviations on planes, Klee was interested in conceiving of language pictorially through the various material grounds that supported it. Klee’s mounts provided a similar opportunity as cuneiform tablets, book pages, and store display windows did in allowing the artist to incorporate yet another material ground into

⁶³ Novalis 1997, S. 83

⁶⁴ Margaret Mahoney Stoljar 1997, S. 7 See also Frank 2004

the work of art and its epistemological content.⁶⁵ For Klee, a given material was embedded with processes one could harness if they attended closely to it. His paperboard mounts in 1920-23 transferred both visual and semantic data, which provided the artist with a way of reconceiving the work of art as a form of Romantic thought rooted in his memories. *E*'s mount title "recalls" the process used in creating the image of *E*: a restrictive overpainting of the artist's otherwise fantastical and delicate fragments, ultimately originating in Klee's work at Schleiheim. With his memories locked behind an inexpressible event, Klee enacted the inability of language to fully convey meaning while at the same time affirming that truth could be found in mental association.

Part 2: A Title-scape

While a Klee title could become a visually charged part of the work of art in a manner that extended its enactment of mental processes like memory and language formation, Klee's late series titles performed an increasingly determinate function in his work and included references to the artist's creative process, which Klee cast in one series as his navigation of a physical space. To interpret Klee's work in exile (1933-1940), a period in which the artist said little about his creations, the following analysis draws comparisons to other works in this period as well as previous practices that he may have been referencing. In works from the last full year of his life (1939), Klee was able not only to create novel integrations of word and image, but also to present new syntheses of his images. In the year immediately preceding his death, Klee's production saw an increase in titles linking drawings in his now primarily graphic oeuvre. In addition to being greater in number, these discursive connections grew in variety and

⁶⁵ Just a few of the enormous variety of examples: Klee created an *Urkunde* (1933, 283), or "Document" out of plaster and watercolor that appears similar to a cuneiform tablet, and a *Window Display for Lingerie* (1922, 125) with translucent blue watercolor washes mimicking the appearance of a shop window.

complexity. The most famous of these titled series are 1939's *The Inferner Park*, the *Näherungen*, or *Approximations*, and a group of related works in 1940 that Klee dubbed the *Engel Folge*, or "Angel Suite." Klee's *Näherungen* are comprised of lines that appear to approach the contours of objects but do not ever fully join to form them, while *The Inferner Park* references Dante's *Inferno* in both its name and the landscape-like features of its constituent drawings. The figures that Klee designates as "angels" in his titles all bear winglike appendages. These series have been extensively studied, yet it is less clear why Klee started to connect his late drawings through series titles, or what their different breeds of linkages entail for their interpretation.⁶⁶

Klee may have created more connections across different drawings through titles in 1939 because he was working on his drawings in quick succession, at an average of approximately 3.5 per day.⁶⁷ This incredibly accelerated production rate compared to previous years had its roots in the historical circumstances surrounding the artist's "late work," a stylistic distinction for his oeuvre between 1937 and 1940, the year of his death.⁶⁸ Paul Klee went into exile in Bern upon being fired from his teaching position at the Düsseldorf Academy of Fine Arts in 1933, shortly after the Nazi rise to power.⁶⁹ In 1935, Klee began to suffer from scleroderma, a disease that progressively hardens the skin and the internal organs.⁷⁰ Estranged not only from his former public but also from his own body, the world was increasingly slipping out of Klee's grasp.

⁶⁶ One interpreter who does pay keen attention to the differences between different kinds of series in Klee's late work is Ann Temkin, who interprets the "Angel Suite" as similarly referencing Klee's creative process. Temkin 1989; Glaesemer 1979

⁶⁷ Klee listed 1,253 works in the 1939 catalogue. Josef Helfenstein and Christian Rümelin, *Paul Klee: catalogue raisonné / herausgegeben von der Paul-Klee-Stiftung, Kunstmuseum Bern; [Projektleitung, Josef Helfenstein, Christian Rümelin]*. 9 Vols. New York: Thames and Hudson, 2004, 554.

⁶⁸ Kathryn E. Kramer, "Myth, Invisibility, and Politics in the Late Work of Paul Klee," in *Languages of Visuality: Crossings between Science, Art, Politics, and Literature*, Kritik (Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 1996), 175.

⁶⁹ Klee 1962, S. 69–70

⁷⁰ Werckmeister 1985, S. 31

Additionally, during the first few years of his exile, Klee's work did not draw the same level of public success in Europe as it had in previous years. In the 1935 exhibition at the Kunsthalle Bern and Kunsthalle Basel, almost none of the artist's works were sold.⁷¹ Towards the beginning of 1938, however, Klee had begun to experience a dramatic turnaround in the sale of his works, most notably in the United States through the efforts of his dealers Curt Valentin and Karl Nierendorf.⁷² Klee was once again in the position of a renowned modern artist, although he was also in deteriorating health and would never again achieve the kind of acknowledgement from the art establishment in Germany where he had previously built his reputation.⁷³ It was in this context that Klee experienced a surge of motivation and created his largest and most intertwined body of work in the year 1939.

Jürgen Glaesemer, the former curator of the Paul-Klee-Stiftung (today the Zentrum Paul Klee), surmised that many of the late drawings must have been "same-day productions," pointing to the artist's statement above the three hundred and sixty-fifth entry in his oeuvre catalogue for 1939—*nulla dies sine linea*, or "no day without a line"—suggesting that Klee was drawing every day.⁷⁴ Will Grohmann recalled Klee associating his drawing practice in this period with the rhythmic, constant, and repetitive feeling of beating a drum.⁷⁵ The accelerated nature of his production caused the borders between Klee's works to blur, with figures, compositions, and styles becoming more uniform and repetitive across his drawings. Tilman Osterwold relates how this altered practice may have provided a fulfilment of the artist's interest in the process of movement as a fundamental creative principle, allowing the process of the work of art's genesis

⁷¹ Werckmeister 1985, S. 30

⁷² Werckmeister 1985, S. 35

⁷³ Werckmeister 1985, S. 27

⁷⁴ Glaesemer, *Paul Klee. Handzeichnungen.*, 3: 25.

⁷⁵ Will Grohmann, *Paul Klee* (Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer, c1954), 347.

to be recorded sequentially in his “diarylike” drawings.⁷⁶ This process would join reworking as a moment in Klee’s creative activity to which his titles refer.

What we see in Klee’s series titles of 1939-40 is likely the result of the artist realizing this quality of his own works and formalizing it into an explicit structural principle that his titles also recall. Given his keen interest in Picasso during this period, Klee’s engagement with presenting his drawings in series may have been influenced in part by the younger artist.⁷⁷ Both men’s forms had begun to merge with one another when the artists were working at an increased pace. One of the many volumes of *Cahiers d’Art* that Klee owned was dedicated almost entirely to Picasso, featuring large cycles of his Surrealist compositions.⁷⁸ Several of Klee’s groups of related drawings he created in the following year, including the *Urchs* series, display a stylistic kinship with Picasso.⁷⁹ Both men were additionally involved in creating their own catalogues at the time, yet Picasso’s was an enterprise of arranging his compositions in visual concert with one another while Klee’s catalogue remained primarily textual. Where Picasso presented his works of art in a grid with one another, Klee created a kind of virtual simultaneity in conceptually linking his compositions with series titles.

As he integrated his mounts with the work of art through his unique titling practice of reprising the spatial relations in a composition, so did Klee in his exile years interweave the sequential ordering structure of his catalogue with his drawings through their titles. Like *E (fragmentary Watercolor)*, the later groups of drawings reveal what Klee’s “associations” could offer the artist as a medium to shape conceptual frameworks for his compositions. In *The*

⁷⁶ Osterwold 1990, S. 27–28

⁷⁷ Christine Hopfengart et al., eds., *Klee trifft Picasso* (Ostfildern: Hatje Cantz, 2010), 55–58.

⁷⁸ *Cahiers d’Art - Revue d’Art: Sondernummer Picasso - El Greco* (1938).

⁷⁹ The title *Urchs* is pun on the German word for “ox” (*Ochse*), and a likely reference to Picasso’s recurring Minotaur/bull artistic persona. See Hopfengart, 218-19.

Inferner Park (1939, 238-253), Klee led his viewer through drawings in the series as if they were parts of a single landscape composition. This imparted to the viewer that the spaces between Klee's drawings could themselves become part of the work of art, even when these works were not at first listed with the intent of comprising a continuous series.

The Inferner Park

The Inferner Park encompasses sixteen 1939 drawings, marked as a connected series with a bracket around their sequential listings in Klee's catalogue. He also wrote *Der Inferner Park*: before each individual work's title on its mount. Marcel Franciscono, who has written most extensively on the series, interprets it as Klee's reflection on the afterlife in the face of his worsening illness.⁸⁰ *The Inferner Park* references Dante's *Inferno*, the first book of his *Divine Comedy* (1321) in which Dante and Virgil descend through the levels of Hell. The title of the series is likely Klee's statement that his own journey into the afterlife was near—it can be translated as “not far.” As Franciscono has pointed out, the series has a strong autobiographical component that can be felt in its titles.

By 1939, Klee likely knew that he would not recover from his disease, which is evident in the dejected tone of his titles, proclaiming a *fruitless Return* (1939, 249) and mentioning that a ship leads to *doubtful Salvation* (1939, 252). For an artist who was progressively becoming alienated from his own body, an image like souls who committed suicide turned into trees and nested in by harpies in Canto XIII of the *Inferno* would have spoken to his growing sense of vulnerability and immobility.⁸¹ The uniting of figural and landscape elements in the drawings attests to this attitude that Klee may have had towards his physical state. Just as Dante plunges

⁸⁰ Franciscono 1991, S. 320

⁸¹ Dante Alighieri, *Inferno*, trans. Robert Hollander, 1st ed. (London: Doubleday, 2000), Canto XIII, ll. 20–51.

spirits in his vision of hell into rivers of blood and burning holes in the ground, so Klee grafts his figures into landscape, as with *die Gegend zur Reue (the Area of Repentance)* (1939, 243) (Figure 6), in which Klee added eyes and nostrils to an otherwise completely non-figural series of curves evoking a rock formation. Like Klee, Dante was in exile while he composed his vision of hell, a connection that Klee may have considered when forming his own reflections on his status in 1939.

The title *The Inferner Park* also reflects on the series' process of creation. Dante's *Inferno* acts as a reference point for individual drawings in the series, and the way its author employs allegory additionally informs the structure of *The Inferner Park* as a whole. As a microcosm of Klee's creative practice, *The Inferner Park* implies that Klee interacted with his own work as a site that provoked narrative speculation. In his serial practice, Klee saw the potential for multiple discrete images to link together under the banner of narrative. Gérard Genette defines narrative as the "signifier, statement, discourse or narrative text itself" that communicates a "story" (*histoire*), or the "signified or narrative content."⁸² Tzvetan Todorov tells us that a narrative links a "continuum of facts and relations" in causal or temporal sequence, and that change occurs in between these elements to constitute a plot.⁸³ As Manfred Faust has pointed out, earlier titles tended more often to describe an element of the image or its physical condition, and later titles frequently seemed to suggest a "situation or a scene."⁸⁴ Klee's series titles did so in a variety of ways, which a precise definition of narrative can help clarify.

Narrativity is an important element present in *The Inferner Park* connected to Klee's serial

⁸² Genette 1990, S. 27

⁸³ Todorov 1971, S. 39

⁸⁴ Manfred Faust, "Entwicklungsstadien der Wortwahl in den Bildtiteln von Klee," *Deutsche Vierteljahrsschrift Für Literaturwissenschaft und Geistesgeschichte* 48, no. 1 (1974): 105–6. Translated by the author.

practice that warrants addressing, however, the potential for narrative was not the only element of Klee's practice that the title engages.

The seeming disjointedness between consecutive "stations" in *The Inferner Park* like the first landscape images and the blossom with its vase has led Franciscono to surmise that these drawings were not originally composed with the intention of unifying them in a series.⁸⁵ Klee seems to return to the beginning of Dante's narrative in his work titled *das Schiff zur zweifelhaftem Rettung (the Ship of Dubious Salvation)* (1939, 252) (Figure 7) directly before his *Scene Towards the End* (1939, 253). Charon ferries the wandering souls across the river Acheron at the beginning of *The Inferno*, not the end.⁸⁶ K. Porter Aichele's attempt to interpret *The Inferner Park* as a "nonconsecutive visual narrative" seems to fit nicely with the artist's other evocations of narrative in his oeuvre, but neither her nor Franciscono's accounts fully encapsulate the particular types of discontinuous relationships between images and their titles in *The Inferner Park*.⁸⁷ Although it plays with narrativity, a larger unifying feature in the series is something like allegory: in this case, a hellish park symbolizes Klee's artistic process as well as his inner turmoil in exile.

Narrative was not a monolith for Klee, as we can see by comparing *The Inferner Park* to another group of drawings of the same period that engages narrative in a different way. In *The Inferner Park*, titles do much of the series' heavy narrative lifting. The preposition "zu" ("to/towards") in multiple titles creates a sense of forward movement in space and time. Singular image titles sometimes reference points within the story of the *Inferno*, marking it as a possible diegesis in which events within the series could transpire. For example, the *Mord-Stelle*, or

⁸⁵ Franciscono 1991, S. 316

⁸⁶ Franciscono also notices the ominous ambiguity at the "end" of the series. See Franciscono 1991, S. 320

⁸⁷ Aichele 2002, S. 43

Murder-Place (1939, 250) could refer to the seventh circle in Dante's poem, where those who have committed violence against their neighbors reside, and *zu den Winden (to the Winds)* (1939, 248), to the gale that blows the lustful in Canto V.⁸⁸⁸⁹ Quotation marks around many of the individual titles following *der Inferner Park*: likewise signify that the phrases within them originated in the text of a larger story that does not appear and is not evident in the form of the works, alone. These titles are evocations of a narrative that is external to the images: if they were not present, one would not be able to reconstruct any element of events in Dante's poem.

In this respect, the series differs from a group of drawings that Klee created in the same year whose sequencing through Klee's work numbers forms another distinct kind of narrativity: successive temporal changes that parallel events in a story. Each drawing in a sequence corresponds to a basic unit of a story: a state of events at a particular time. In 1939, Klee drew a wolflike snouted creature with beady eyes and small pointed ears. Skewering a fish with its fork, the animal opens its mouth in anticipation of a meal. The title of the drawing reads *mir Hering?! (Herring, for me?!)* (Figure 8). The next work Klee entered in his catalogue carries the title *nie mehr jene Speise!, or never again such food!* (Figure 9) and depicts a creature with almost the exact same facial features yet without a paw clutching a utensil. Klee used the titles of these drawings to create both a change and a continuity between his works, thereby crafting a narrative. For a narrative composed of change to be recognizable as a coherent totality, it requires an element that remains constant. In this case, the "character" depicted forms this continuity for our story. This constancy then allows one to form the notion that a change has transpired. Only if one assumes that the animal in the successive drawings is the same does it

⁸⁸ Dante Alighieri, *Inferno*, trans. Robert Hollander, 1st ed. (London: Doubleday, 2000), Canto XII.

⁸⁹ Dante Alighieri, *Inferno*, Canto V, ll. 30–39.

become possible to conclude that the canid's action of holding up a paw with food temporally precedes the drawing including only the creature's head.

The titles lead us to this connection by bringing in information external to the images that connects them to a larger sequence of events, or diegesis. The title *Herring, for me?!* implies that the creature is speaking to someone who gave it the herring before the first drawing "occurred." There is an invisible agent not depicted who nonetheless exists in the story-world. In this sequence of two works, Klee's titles serve a function that Roland Barthes termed "relay." In relay, "text (most often a snatch of dialogue) and image stand in a complementary relationship; the words, in the same way as the images, are fragments of a more general syntagm and the unity of the message is realized at a higher level, that of the story, the anecdote, the diegesis." Barthes describes relay as occurring most often in comics and film, where text or recorded voices form parallel continuities.⁹⁰ The text in a comic strip or in a film pushes the narrative forward by relaying each successive image's relation to its predecessor and to the story as a whole. The impression of a temporal succession of events in the dog-series is accomplished through qualities internal to the works, in addition to their placement one after the other.

In *The Inferner Park*, on the other hand, continuity and change both come largely through the "zu" in many of the series titles. This evocation of progression does not appear in all of the individual drawing titles in the series, however. Additionally, other than their very basic similarity in the fragmented linear style common to most of Klee's late drawings, one would be hard pressed to identify a clear narrative connection between drawings like *to the Premature Rest* (Figure 10) and *The Ship to Dubious Salvation*. Seeing these images and their titles, one is tempted to label the series a series of illustrations to the story in Dante's *Inferno*, but the order of

⁹⁰ Barthes 2009, S. 157

the drawings and Klee's refusal to include clear references to places or actions in the *Inferno* in every title resists this interpretation. To repurpose the *Inferno* as his own creative realm cues us in to Klee's *allegorical* thinking about his own work, rather than his narrative thinking. The story of Dante's *Inferno* was one among multiple different references that *The Inferner Park* contains. Klee's single title of *The Inferner Park* also speaks to his associations relating to the artist's more serial creative practice that led to the creation of groups in the first place.

My reading of *The Inferner Park* as Klee's allegory for his own creative process is grounded in the artist's presentation of himself as harnessing natural forces in his works. His choice to name the series *Park* is telling in the context of the artist's writings. In Klee's lecture to the Jena *Kunstverein* in 1924, the artist expressed that he was akin to the trunk of a tree, a channel between underlying basic nutrients of creative development and the viewer.⁹¹ Other drawings from the exile years show that Klee had returned to this natural metaphor for his compositions. One sees this in the drawing depicting leaves with figural forms inscribed on them that Klee titled *figurale Blätter* (1938, 468), punning on the shared meaning of the term *Blatt* as a leaf and a page.⁹² The work is a likely reference to the artist's own predominantly figural compositions on sheets of paper in his final years, especially since *Blatt* was also a term that the artist had used for his works on paper in his catalogue. In the case of *The Inferner Park*, Klee made a similarly self-referential statement about his oeuvre. He figured it as the larger "park" for which he acted as a kind of gardener in guiding the natural growth processes of his forms.

Klee's drawings comprising *The Inferner Park* do not present too obvious of a unifying principle besides that which this repeated title imposes on the works. However, one can identify some internal connections in the series beginning with the first drawing. The series opens with a

⁹¹ Klee 1966, S. 13

⁹² For an explanation of this pun as it relates to Klee's earlier work, See Bourneuf 2015, S. 14

work entitled *d. Inferner Park: "eingangs,"* (*The Inferner Park: on entering*) (1939, 238) (Figure 11), featuring a figure astride a mountainous form – a possible reference to the hill Dante approaches at the beginning of the *Inferno*.⁹³ The following five works seem to connect to this one in that they, too, reproduce landscape forms. A sun-like circle among clouds in *First Level* (1939, 239) (Figure 12), for example, reappears in the following drawing, *to the Premature Rest* (1939, 240). The following three drawings—*to the Luxuriance* (1939, 241) (Figure 13), *at the Apparent Bridging* (1939, 242) (Figure 14), and *the Area of Repentance* (1939, 243) (Figure 15)—all to some extent include the elongated vertical and horizontal ovoid forms on their borders that *to the Premature Rest* exhibited. Thus far, one can identify continuities in the landscape forms throughout several of *The Inferner Park*'s smaller subgroups.

The Inferner Park transforms Klee's oeuvre into a continuous landscape by likening his arrangement of creations in the catalogue to the physical manicuring of bushes and trees in a park. Throughout his career, Klee cut his drawings apart to make new compositions listed separately in the catalogue. We saw one example of a sheared composition in *Fragment from a Ballet to Aeolian Harp*, which referred to its own status as a "cutout," or even a "clipping" (*Ausschnitt*). Klee also combined separate works to create new larger compositions.⁹⁴ In their thorough analysis of Klee's cut-apart and recombined images, Osamu Okuda and Wolfgang Kersten showed that this process was, like Klee's cataloguing, a multivalent one that he could use to reconceive the work of art in different ways.⁹⁵

⁹³ Dante Alighieri, *Inferno*, 1st ed. (London: Doubleday, 2000), Canto I, 3.

⁹⁴ Wolfgang Kersten and Osamu Okuda, *Paul Klee : im Zeichen der Teilung : die Geschichte zerschnittener Kunst Paul Klees 1883-1940, mit vollständiger Dokumentation : Kunstsammlung Nordrhein-Westfalen, Düsseldorf, 21. Januar bis 17. April 1995, Staatsgalerie Stuttgart, 29. April bis 23. Juli 1995* (Stuttgart: Hatje, 1995), 12-13.

⁹⁵ Kersten and Okuda, 19, 57.

In *The Inferner Park*, Klee figures both processes, performing “cuts” and recombinations of works that he implies to have previously formed continuous wholes. Klee’s first enactment of his processes of severance comes with his separation *The Blossom of Narcosis* (Figure 16) from its partner, titled *Vase N* (Figure 17). While the drawings likely never constituted an actual physical whole, Klee conceptually reconstructed for them a previous unity by distinguishing their style from other members of the series. These drawings are vertically oriented, unlike their neighbors, and do not seem to include any landscape elements. Klee had referred to the undulating style in which he fashioned these compositions as “baroque,” likely referencing the proliferations of curls and ornamentation in baroque art and furnishings.⁹⁶ Through his titles for these similar drawings, Klee cast their distance from one another in the catalogue as the removal of flowers from a vase. The separation between *the blossom of narcosis* and *Vase N* created by the insertion of *to the Mother’s Fear* (1939, 245) between them was evidently quite important to Klee, who had made an error in his mount numbers for the works but returned to correct the mistake, reasserting this division. This process of splitting was not the only one Klee used in *The Inferner Park*, but also presenting us with disparate drawings that are made whole by their titles.

We see this in the relationship between two sequential drawings in the series, *to the Rupture* (1939, 247) (Figure 18) and *to the Winds* (1939, 248) (Figure 19), and a watercolor on primed burlap removed from *The Inferner Park* by a few work numbers but given the same name (1939, 255) (Figure 20). *To Rupture* and *to the Winds* reproduce almost exactly the forms in the watercolor *The Inferner Park*, appearing as though they might have been either traced from the larger work or used as sketches for it. There would be precedent for either possibility in Klee’s creative practice. Klee sometimes created a singular composition out of separate parts, as he did

⁹⁶ Franciscono 1991, S. 316

with several of his oil-transfer drawings,⁹⁷ and he also cut up existing compositions and listed the resulting pieces separately in his oeuvre catalogue.⁹⁸ In both cases, Klee used existing works to generate new ones and then listed all these compositions in his catalogue. What distinguishes the works in *The Inferner Park* from others that Klee separates and recombines is their shared titling. He does not create new compositions but implies that the drawings are part of the same overall pictorial scheme. By giving the singular work *The Inferner Park* the same title as the series designation in his catalogue, as well as placing shared compositional elements in both, Klee gives a discursive link the status of a spatial continuity. Through this parallel, the series *The Inferner Park* becomes not a narrative but a place.

Although *The Inferner Park* references Klee's "use of the cut," as Okuda and Kersten have called it, *The Inferner Park* uses cutting and resuturing through the catalogue in a different way than Klee had engaged them before.⁹⁹ At earlier moments in his career, Klee rarely ever directly implied that consecutive drawings that had been cut from the same original composition.¹⁰⁰ In his titles, Klee did often reflect on a cut to make a visual pun, like he did with *Excerpt from a Ballet to Aeolian Harp*. In his earlier work, however, the artist did not generally make use of the catalogue's potential to recombine images sequentially and mark this through their titles. There is one notable exception—*Between Pirla and Pal* (1924, 181), originally situated between *Pirla* (1924, 179), and *PAL* (1924, 180).¹⁰¹ These fragments once constituted a larger whole. By placing them next to one another in his catalogue, Klee approached what he did

⁹⁷ One example of Klee combining two oil transfer drawings into one work is *Fischbild* (1925, 5); see discussion of this process in Rümelin 2001, S. 27

⁹⁸ For detailed analyses of Klee's cut works, see Kersten/Okuda 1995

⁹⁹ Kersten/Okuda 1995, S. 11

¹⁰⁰ Kersten/Okuda 1995, S. 13

¹⁰¹ Kersten/Okuda 1995, S. 13

with *The Inferner Park*. He made a conceptual link between their proximity in a list to their former physical cohesion, and then marked this connection with the watercolors' titles.

This comparison reflects on how Klee might have increasingly viewed his compositions as a potential continuity. Numbering in a series could serve the same purpose as the visible, concrete connections between forms within Klee's works. The commonality of style as well as the unity of title across the large watercolor *The Inferner Park* and the series *The Inferner Park* created an equivalency between contours spanning the surface of a work of art and the imaginary throughlines offered by Klee's catalogue. His daily drawing habit likely allowed the artist to let his mind wander down pathways in his drawings and find unexpected connections between them, and *The Inferner Park* stakes out his oeuvre as a space for us to do the same.

The mounts of individual works in *The Inferner Park* series further suggest that the artist had adopted this attitude, treating the connections between compositions in a similar manner as he did individual forms. One finds evidence of this in Klee's pencil provisional titles on the mounts. Klee would push his interpretations of a single form in different directions when it appeared in different works, as he did with a gearlike element that becomes a cogwheel in *Still life with the Cog-wheel* (1934, 52), and a spool in *No thread* (1934, 53). From the mounts of works in *The Inferner Park*, it becomes clear that Klee reconceived the links between his drawings to reference spatial qualities more explicitly. He moved them towards a reflection of specific locations in Dante's story of a journey through the circles of hell. For example, Klee originally titled the first work in the series *Park Infern: zur Versuchung* (*Park Infern: to Temptation*) yet subsequently changed its title to *Eingangs* (*entrance*), and implied that his series, like Dante's version of hell, had an entrance on a mountain. *Park Infern: allzubewegt* (*Park Infern: all too moved*) also turns into *to the Winds*, a possible reference to the winds in

Dante's *Inferno* tormenting souls who committed the sin of lust.¹⁰² This amounts to a shared treatment of inter- and intra-compositional elements in Klee's titles, suggesting that the linkages between his works in his catalogue were potential extensions in space. Klee was likely first inspired to create the series not out of thin air, but through looking back at his varied drawings and progressively conceiving of links between them to be formalized in a series title. In the case of *The Inferner Park*, this connection was manifestly spatial, but the altered titles tell us that it need not have always been so. In thematizing Klee's own method of crossing disparate sets of works, *The Inferner Park* conveys that the viewer could also chart their own journey through the "Park" of Klee's oeuvre in choosing which works occupy the same conceptual space. Drawing this conclusion from *The Inferner Park* can help us circumvent the interpretive dead-end of trying to streamline these works into narrative.

Another question remains about the relationship between *The Inferner Park*'s title and its constituent drawings. Why not include more references to figures in the titles or forms of a series referencing a poem that places so much of its focus on the physical torments that individual sinners suffer? It could be that Klee was simply more interested in Dante's spatial configuration of hell, with its distinct circles that the modern artist would echo in discrete pages, but I find this explanation unsatisfying. The majority of Klee's drawings in 1939 contain figures, and he was clearly intensely occupied with questions of physiognomy that had interested him much earlier in his career. Charles W. Haxthausen has dubbed Klee's broader engagement with these ideas in the late work as a "physiognomy of the entire image."¹⁰³ I would posit that the extent of the titles' reference to Klee's own creative process in his exile years does encompass the figural, albeit in a different way than in many other drawings. Klee, an artist living with and through his

¹⁰² Alighieri 2000

¹⁰³ Haxthausen 1990, S. 33

increasingly fragmented pencil lines, may have seen a single line as having an enhanced degree of independent agency and life.

For example, take to *Fruitless Return* (1939, 249) (Figure 21). The title suggests that something is turning around and returning from whence it came, without success, but what exactly is it that turns around? To answer this, we could follow the line that takes a walk from the rightmost form down its long sojourn across the bottom of the page and back up into one of several fingerlike protrusions. This stroke reaches a turning point when it nears the cloudish boundary shape at the top of the page, weaving left until it ducks back down and then makes another attempt to veer left again, only to double back once more. Although these lines turn in multiple directions over the course of Klee's long, uninterrupted pencil movements, the main pattern of movement they have in common that likely reminded the artist of an *Umkehr*, or "reversal," is that of going left and then right. The term *Umkehr* could be understood in multiple senses; it could mean a literal about-face or a changing of the mind. Although less frequently used as such, *Umkehr* could also mean a spiritual repentance before the end. Klee may have thought that his line appeared as though it had resolved to go left, but then realized the error of its ways and decided to move right, or vice versa. The title here personifies the line without an accompanying alteration of line clarifying a figure, as was likely the case in *The area of Rest* (1939, 243).

Like people, Klee's lines could act well or badly. Physiognomy in the caricature that Klee so admired earlier in life and to which he returned in many of his late works connected outward appearance to inner character.¹⁰⁴ Each line comprising a face could veer from the straight and narrow path into a deceitful grin. Klee's titles sometimes make judgments about the actions that

¹⁰⁴ For Klee's return to caricature in the late work, see Temkin 1989

these personified lines take. The designation of *zur Üppigkeit* (1939, 241), or *to the Luxuriance*, attributes the sin of excess to lines that do not just dutifully approach their destination as a representational object, like those of his 1939 *Näherung*, or *Approximation* series, whose full title in Klee's catalogue is *Näherung an den Gegenstand*, or *Approximation/Getting-Closer-To the Object*. Rather, the lines in *zur Üppigkeit* luxuriate in their idle refusal to make something of themselves. This excess has been punished, it seems, by the image's placement in *The Inferner Park*.

Klee was tracing a great meandering line through his drawings, following it as it made an *Attempt as a Plant* (1939, 590) or broke off from a "mother" figure to beget offspring in *Mutter und Töchter (Mother and Daughters)* (Figure 22), twisting and turning into lifelike creatures.

Line was previously given a kind of human agency by Klee through his statements in *Creative Credo* ("Schöpferische Konfession") (1920):

Let us develop this idea, let us take a little trip into the land of deeper insight, following a topographic plan. The dead centre being the point, our first dynamic act will be the line. After a short time, we shall stop to catch our breath (the broken line, or the line articulated by several stops). I look back to see how far we have come (counter-movement). Ponder the distances thus far travelled (sheaf of lines). A river may obstruct our progress: we use a boat (wavy line). Further on there might be a bridge (series of curves). On the other bank we encounter someone who, like us, wishes to deepen his insight. At first we joyfully travel together (convergence), but gradually differences arise (two lines drawn independently of each other). Each party shows some excitement (expression, dynamism, emotional quality of the line).¹⁰⁵

Klee puts the viewer in the position of the point as it travels on the picture plane, enacting the temporal as well as spatial process of sequential viewing that he wanted his images to elicit. Klee outlines a similar "journey" for his points and lines in *The Inferner Park*, with a particularly similar image of a bridge as a series of arches in *to the apparent Bridging* (1939, 242). Rather than reaching the "land of better understanding," however, these lines remain stranded *in der*

¹⁰⁵ Klee/Gale 2013, S. 7

Ferne (“in the distance”), helplessly removed from wherever they are trying to go. Like the title *Näherung*, the name *der Inferner Park* carries the trace of these works’ creator seeing them as stranded in a state removed from fully independent being.

Klee’s position relative to his work that he expresses in his titles would also have been similar to that of an animator: day after day, he drew hundreds of sketches to which he would then prescribe an ordered sequence. Some of Klee's drawings in 1938 and 1939 even involve a simulation of movement achieved through the sequential juxtaposition of drawings similar to the economized line progressing in rapid succession in animation.¹⁰⁶ Ultimately, they gained a biomorphic quality that Sergei Eisenstein called "plasmaticity," which he ascribed paradigmatically to Disney cartoons. Eisenstein defines "plasmaticness" as the quality of line being somehow always in nascent pre-developmental form, capable of stretching and metamorphosing into anything. Although it is chiefly to be found in cartoons, Eisenstein also ascribes this quality to static drawings by artists and illustrators from Wilhelm Busch to Picasso. In their work, just as in Klee’s, the "unity of an object and the form of its representation is dissected," as "the contour, the outline of a drawing - its generalizing line, suddenly begins to take on an independent life, independent of the figures themselves, the objects themselves."¹⁰⁷ It is this kind of life that Klee possibly saw in his images, making the curves in *Blossom of*

¹⁰⁶ See, for example, the series of drawings listed sequentially in Klee’s catalogue that includes *Kluges Kind* (1938 322), *nicht ohne Schärpen* (1938 323), *Plumpsack* (1938 325), *Schreck-Stellung* (1938 326), and *lächelndes Tierchen* (1938 337). This series seems to depict a metamorphosis occurring between one drawing and the next. Two spaces after listing a drawing with the greatest number of recognizable features that form the *Gestalt* of a face (*Erstwhile Charming*, or *weiland Reizend* (1938 324), Klee listed a drawing that he titles *Bewegtes*, or *Moving* (1938 327) (a neuter subject is implied in the original German). Klee played out a narrative of the process of these forms trying to reconstitute their lost original physiognomy. The element that changes in this “story” is the lines, and the smile marks narrative continuity. Decoupling visual constancy from change, the smile allows the lines that surround it the freedom to bend and move themselves.

¹⁰⁷ Sergei M. Eisenstein, *Eisenstein on Disney*, ed. Jay Leyda. London: Methuen, 1988, 58-59.

Narcosis (1939, 244), *Vase N* (1939, 246), and *the Ship of dubious Salvation* (1939, 252) capable of suffering and necessitating their placement in a netherworld.

Some drawings in the series describe the landscape of *The Inferner Park*, and some belong in the series because they contain lines that simply look tortured. Although there are closed forms present in three of the greatest outliers in the series, the *Blossom of Narcosis* (1939, 244), *Vase N* (1939, 246), and *the Ship of dubious Salvation* (1939, 252), all of them feature lines that seem to be squirming, restlessly struggling against their constraints. In *The Ship to Dubious Salvation*, for example, the shape of a ship's hull is clearly visible in the lower portion of the form depicted, but the lines throughout this "ship" are teeming with life. They change direction and curl unpredictably, traveling up in at least four instances to form what look like they could be the beginnings of passengers' heads, but never quite succeed. A series for Klee could be a physical space and a conceptual classification at the same time, becoming as animate and multifaceted as his lines, themselves.

As his drawings grew more and more intertwined during his year of extraordinary productivity, Klee's titling practice shifted in accordance and reflected this trend. Even if the creation of such series may have been a possibility for Klee in his earlier work, he did not often seize upon the opportunity to form them. The much-increased appearance of sequential series like *The Inferner Park* in the late work was likely due to the change that had occurred in his oeuvre. By 1939, works in Klee's catalogue formed more of an unbroken continuity. As a result, Klee may have viewed the borders of a page as more fluid than they had been before, and this shift resulted in an increase of sequential groupings through titles. In this practice, like the characters at the end of *Candide* (1759), the novel for which Klee made his first series of illustrations, the artist sought a form of recreating and shaping the world in miniature as an

antidote to what was certainly not the “best of all possible worlds.”¹⁰⁸ It was in tending his garden, in shearing and cross-pollinating it through his titling practice, that Klee brought about the ordered genesis of new artistic forms. In its references to this process, *The Inferner Park*’s title became a “ground” for the figure of the artwork.

Conclusion

Paul Klee was deeply involved in the construction of his own public artistic persona throughout his career, which at certain moments necessitated the revision and renewal of older work in the early 1920s. The act of reflection on his own artistic process and, with it, notions of the work of art, became a key interest for Klee that continued into his late work. Klee’s keen ability to observe his own work from a remove as his own viewer, evident in his 1924 Jena Lecture, carried over into the kinds of “associations” he made in his titles. Ultimately, however, Klee would never be able to fully alienate himself from his own knowledge of how a work came into being. His designations on the mounts and in his catalogue, so crucial for a full appreciation of Klee’s art, responded not only to the forms present in the work but also to the processes used to create them. In at least two distinct points in his career, the First World War and its immediate aftermath as well as the year 1939, the “associations” that Paul Klee formed with his own work in his titles reflected moments in their journey toward balanced resolution. Studying the reflexivity of Klee’s titles leads to an enriched understanding of the ways that the artist potentially conceived of the idea of art. In approximately 1918-23, with *E*, a title could blur the distinction between the artwork and its surroundings, Klee could harness the title’s associative power to make a connection between the mental and material worlds through analogizing the creation of a name and the titling of an image. In 1939, as Klee created a large body of work at

¹⁰⁸ Ann Temkin mentions *Candide* as a possible precursor to late series like *The Inferner Park*. Temkin 1989, S. 142

an astonishing pace, his process evolved such that he began composing on the level of more than one image. *The Inferner Park*'s title contains a trace of this practice in representing Klee's oeuvre and its interrelated forms as the hellscape of his exile.

This type of reflexive title is one among many for Klee; I have not attempted to form a unified theory of all, or even most, of his various kinds of titles over the course of his long career. The notion of representativeness is not always appropriate for an artist whose work is so incredibly varied. Interpretations of Klee's work and titling practice can benefit from attempting to answer exactly what an "association" could have entailed for Klee at different points in his career. One could investigate dozens of other fascinating works from different periods in Klee's life whose titles have not been given enough attention in their interpretation. *Katastrophe J □ 4* (*Catastrophe J □ 4*) (1925, 184), for example, uses "J4" as a title, catalogue number, and central formal element, and Klee placed a small image in lieu of a title on the drawing's mount in *Ballon Windmesser, Fahne, Gestirne* (*Balloon, windsock, flag, stars*) (1917, 17). These images show the artist using his "associations" in ways that not only augment his compositions but also invite new conceptualizations of discursive information surrounding the work of art.

Bibliography

Aichele 2002

K. Porter Aichele, *Paul Klee's Pictorial Writing*, Cambridge, U.K.; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2002.

Aichele 2006

Kathryn Porter Aichele, *Paul Klee, Poet/Painter*, Rochester, NY: Camden House, 2006.

Alighieri 2000

Dante Alighieri, *Inferno*, translated by Robert Hollander, 1st ed. London: Doubleday, 2000.

Anger 2004

Jenny Anger, *Paul Klee and the Decorative in Modern Art*, New York: Cambridge University Press, 2004.

Bärmann 2003

Matthias Bärmann, *Paul Klee : die Erfüllung im Spätwerk*, Bern : Benteli, 2003.

Barthes 2009

Roland Barthes, "Rhetoric of the Image", in: *Image, music, text*, Nachdr., New York, NY: Hill and Wang, 2009, 32–51.

Barthes 2009

Roland Barthes, transl. by Stephen Heath, *Image, music, text*, Nachdr., New York, NY: Hill and Wang, 2009.

Beiträge Bern 2000

Paul Klee, Kunst und Karriere : Beiträge des internationalen Symposiums in Bern, Bern: Stämpfli, 2000.

Bourneuf 2015

Annie Bourneuf, *Paul Klee: The Visible and the Legible*, Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2015.

Bulckens

Koen Bulckens, "A Brief History of the Catalogue Raisonné", in: *Picturing Ludwig Burchard (1886-1960)*, L. Nijkamp und K. Bulckens, London: Turnhout, 103–114.

Cook 1986

Albert Cook, "The Sign in Klee", in: *Word & Image*, Routledge, 1986, Vol. 2, Issue 4, 363–381.

Craven 1990

Craven, David. "Karl Werckmeister and the Role of Critical Scholarship." *Art Journal* 13, no. 2 (1990): 93–97.

Derrida 1987

Jacques Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1987.

Faust 1974

Manfred Faust, “Entwicklungsstadien der Wortwahl in den Bildtiteln von Klee”, in: *Deutsche Vierteljahrsschrift für Literaturwissenschaft Und Geistesgeschichte*, J.B. Metzler, 1974, Vol. 48, Issue 1, 25–46.

Franciscono 1991

Marcel Franciscono, *Paul Klee: His Work and Thought*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1991.

Freud 2010

Freud, Sigmund. *The Interpretation of Dreams*. Translated by James Strachey. New York: Basic Books A Member of the Perseus Books Group, 2010 (originally published 1899).

Geelhaar 1976

Christian Geelhaar (Editor), “Beitrag für den Sammelband >Schöpferische Konfession<”, in: *Schriften : Rezensionen u. Aufsätze*, Köln: DuMont, 1976, 118–122.

Geelhaar 1979

Christian Geelhaar, “Journal intime oder Autobiographie? Über Paul Klees Tagebücher”, in: *Paul Klee: Das Frühwerk 1883-1922.*, ed. Armin Zweite, Munich, 1979, 246–260.

Glaesemer 1987

Glaesemer, Jürgen. “Paul Klee and German Romanticism”, in: *Paul Klee*, edited by Carolyn Lanchner. Boston: Distributed by New York Graphic Society Books/Little, Brown, 1987.

Genette 1990

Gérard Genette, *Narrative discourse: an essay in method*, 1. publ., 4. print, Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1990.

Glaesemer 1979

Jürgen Glaesemer, *Paul Klee. Handzeichnungen.*, Bern: Kunstmuseum, 1979, Vol. 3.

Grohmann 1954

Will Grohmann, *Paul Klee.*, Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer, 1954.

Gombrich 1985

Gombrich, E. H. “Image and Word in Twentieth-Century Art”, in: *Word & Image* 1, no. 3 (July 1, 1985): 213–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02666286.1985.10435861>.

Hausenstein 1921

Wilhelm Hausenstein, *Kairuan, oder, Eine Geschichte vom Maler Klee und von der Kunst dieses Zeitalters*, München: Kurt Wolff, 1921.

Haxthausen 1990

Charles W. Haxthausen, "Zur >>Bildsprache<< des Spätwerkes", in: *Paul Klee, das Schaffen im Todesjahr*, Stuttgart : G. Hatje, 1990.

Haxthausen 1981

Charles Werner Haxthausen, *Paul Klee, the Formative Years*, New York: Garland Pub, 1981.

Helfenstein/Rümelin 2004

Josef Helfenstein und Christian Rümelin, *Paul Klee: Catalogue Raisonné / Herausgegeben Von Der Paul-Klee-Stiftung, Kunstmuseum Bern ; [projektleitung, Josef Helfenstein, Christian Rümelin].*, New York: Thames and Hudson, 2004.

Hopfengart et al. 2010

Christine Hopfengart et al. (Eds.), *Klee trifft Picasso*, Ostfildern: Hatje Cantz, 2010.

Josef Helfenstein/Stefan Frey 1990

Josef Helfenstein and Stefan Frey, *Paul Klee, das Schaffen im Todesjahr*, Stuttgart: G. Hatje, 1990.

Kemp 1995

Wolfgang Kemp, "A Shelter for Paintings", in: *In Perfect Harmony: Picture + Frame, 1850-1920*, Amsterdam, Zwolle: Van Gogh Museum; Waanders Uitgevers, 1995, 13–28.

Kersten/Okuda 1995

Wolfgang Kersten und Osamu Okuda, *Paul Klee : im Zeichen der Teilung : die Geschichte zerschnittener Kunst Paul Klees 1883-1940, mit vollständiger Dokumentation : Kunstsammlung Nordrhein-Westfalen, Düsseldorf, 21. Januar bis 17. April 1995, Staatsgalerie Stuttgart, 29. April bis 23. Juli 1995*, Stuttgart: Hatje, 1995.

Felix Klee 1962

Felix Klee, *Paul Klee, His Life and Work in Documents, Selected from Posthumous Writings and Unpublished Letters*, New York: G. Braziller, 1962.

Felix Klee 1984

Klee, Felix. *Paul Klee, Rosenwind, 25 Farbbilder: 30 Zeichnungen Und Viele Autobiografische Notizen*. Freiburg im Breisgau: Herder, 1984.

Klee 1957

Paul Klee, *Tagebücher von Paul Klee, 1898-1918*, Köln: M. DuMont Schauberg, 1957.

Klee 1960

Paul Klee, *Paul Klee; Leben Und Werk in Dokumenten, Ausgewählt Aus Den Nachgelassenen Aufzeichnungen Und Den Unveröffentlichten Briefen*, edited by Felix Klee, Zürich: Diogenes Verlag, 1960.

Klee 1966

Klee, Paul. *On Modern Art*. Translated by Paul Findlay. Faber Paper Covered Editions. London: Faber, 1966.

Klee 1964b

Paul Klee, *The Diaries of Paul Klee, 1898-1918*, transl. by Felix Klee, Berkeley: University of California Press, 1964.

Klee 1976

Paul Klee, *Schriften : Rezensionen u. Aufsätze*, edited by Christian Geelhaar, Köln: DuMont, 1976.

Klee 1979

Paul Klee, *Briefe an die Familie : 1893-1940*, Köln: DuMont, 1979, Vol. 2.

Klee 2013

Klee, Paul, and Matthew Gale. *Creative Confession and Other Writings*. London: Tate Publishing, 2013.

Kort 2003

Pamela Kort, *Paul Klee 1933*, Köln: König, 2003.

Kramer 1996

Kathryn E. Kramer, "Myth, Invisibility, and Politics in the Late Work of Paul Klee", in: *Languages of visibility: crossings between science, art, politics, and literature*, Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 1996.

Krauss 1981

Krauss, Rosalind. "In the Name of Picasso", in: *October* 16 (1981): 5–22.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/778371>.

Kröll 1968

Kröll, Christina. *Die Bildtitel Paul Klees. Eine Studie Zur Beziehung von Bild Und Sprache in Der Kunst Des Zwanzigsten Jahrhunderts*. Bonn, 1968.
<https://books.google.de/books?id=0jkTAQAAlAAJ>.

Kühn 1990

Matthias Kühn, "'Gewagte Symbiosen' - Bild und Bildtitel im Spätwerk Klees", in: *Paul Klee, das Schaffen im Todesjahr*, Stuttgart : G. Hatje, 1990.

Lessing 2010

Gotthold Ephraim Lessing, *Laokoon oder über die Grenzen der Malerei und Poesie: mit beiläufigen Erläuterungen verschiedener Punkte der alten Kunstgeschichte*, transl. by Ingrid Kreuzer, Bibliogr. erg. Ausg. 1987, [Reprint], Stuttgart: Reclam, 2010.

Novalis 1997

Novalis. *Philosophical Writings*. Edited by Margaret M. Stoljar. Translated by Margaret Mahony Stoljar. Albany, N.Y.: State University of New York Press, 1997.

Okuda 1997

Osamu Okuda, “Paul Klee: Buchhaltung, Werkbezeichnung und Werkprozess”, in: *Radical art history: internationale Anthologie: Subject, O.K. Werckmeister*, edited by Wolfgang Kersten und Joan Weinstein, Zürich: ZIP, 1997, 374–397.

Okuda 2000

Osamu Okuda, “Erinnerungsblick und Revision. Über den Werkprozess Paul Klees in dem Jahren 1919-1923”, in: *Paul Klee, Kunst und Karriere : Beiträge des internationalen Symposiums in Bern*, Bern: Stämpfli, 2000.

Okuda 2003

Osamu Okuda, “Versuche über Honore Daumier’s sichtbaren Einfluss auf Paul Klee”, in: *Paul Klee 1933*, Köln: König, 2003.

Osterwold 1990

Tilman Osterwold, *Paul Klee: Spätwerk*, Stuttgart: G. Hatje, 1990.

Röthel/Kandinsky/Benjamin 1982

Hans Konrad Röthel, Wassily Kandinsky und Jean K. Benjamin, *Kandinsky, Catalogue Raisonné of the Oil-Paintings*, Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell University Press, 1982.

Rottmann 2020

Michael Rottmann, “Paul Klee’s “Honey-Writing” Some Reflections on the Relation of Automatism, Automation, Machines and Mathematics”, in: *Imagine Math 7: Between Culture and Mathematics*, edited by Michele Emmer und Marco Abate, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, s. 5–29.

Rümelin 2001

Christian Rümelin, “Klee’s Interaction with his own Oeuvre”, in: *Paul Klee: Selected by Genius, 1917-1933*, edited by Roland Doschka und Stadthalle Balingen, Munich; New York: Prestel, 2001, 21–38.

Schlegel 1991

Schlegel, Friedrich von. *Philosophical Fragments*. Translated by Peter Edgerly Firchow. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1991.

Schwitters 2021

Schwitters, K. *Myself and My Aims: Writings on Art and Criticism*. Edited by Megan R. Luke. Translated by Timothy Grundy. University of Chicago Press, 2021.
<https://books.google.de/books?id=dXoWEAAAQBAJ>.

Sladeczek 2000

Eva Wiederkehr Sladeczek, “Der handschriftliche Œuvre-Katalog von Paul Klee”, in: *Paul Klee, Kunst und Karriere : Beiträge des internationalen Symposiums in Bern*, Bern: Stämpfli, 2000, 146–158.

Temkin 1989

Ann Temkin, “Die Zeichnungen von 1939 - Werk und Kontext”, in: *Paul Klee : späte Zeichnungen von 1939*, Essen: Museum Folkwang Essen, 1989.

Todorov 1971

Tzvetan Todorov, “The 2 Principles of Narrative”, in: *Diacritics*, Johns Hopkins University Press, 1971, Vol. 1, Issue 1, 37–44.

Trodd 2008

Tamara Trodd, “Drawing in the Archive: Paul Klee’s Oil-Transfers”, in: *Oxford Art Journal*, 2008, Vol. 31, Issue 1, 75–95.

Urban/Nolde 1987

Martin Urban und Emil Nolde, *Emil Nolde: Werkverzeichnis der Gemälde*, München: C.H. Beck, 1987.

Vogel 1992

Marianne Vogel, *Zwischen Wort und Bild: das schriftliche Werk Paul Klees und die Rolle der Sprache in seinem Denken und in seiner Kunst*, Munich: Scaneg, 1992.

Voltaire 2005

Voltaire, *Candide, or Optimism / Voltaire; translated and edited by Theo Cuffe with an introduction by Michael Wood.*, edited by Theo Cuffe, Penguin Books, 2005.

Werckmeister 1981

O. K. Werckmeister, *Versuche über Paul Klee*, Frankfurt am Main: Syndikat, 1981.

Werckmeister 1985

Otto Karl Werckmeister, *Paul Klee in exile, 1933-1940 / [edited and translated by Tadayasu Sakai and others].*, Fuji Television Gallery, 1985.

Werckmeister 1989

Otto Karl Werckmeister, *The Making of Paul Klee’s Career, 1914-1920*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1989.

Wittgenstein 2009

Ludwig Wittgenstein, “Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus”, in: *Major Works: Selected Philosophical Writings*, 1. ed, New York: HarperPerennial, 2009, 1–84.

Yeazell 2016

Yeazell, Ruth Bernard. *Picture Titles. How and Why Western Paintings Acquired Their Names*. Princeton University Press, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400873463>.

Figure 1. Paul Klee (1879-1940), *Ausschnitt aus einem Ballett zur Aeolsharfe* (Excerpt from a Ballet to Aeolian Harp), (1922, 87): Watercolour, pen and pencil on paper on cardboard. 23,5 x 20,3 cm. Museum Sammlung Rosengart, Luzern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv

Figure 2. Paul Klee, *E (fragmentarisches Aquarell)* (*E (fragmentary Watercolor)*), (1918, 199), watercolor and pencil on primed paper on cardboard, 22 x 18 cm, Private Collection, Switzerland, Depot in Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 3. Paul Klee, *E (fragmentarisches Aquarell)* (*E (fragmentary Watercolor)*) (Detail) watercolor and pencil on primed paper on cardboard, 22 x 18 cm, Private Collection, Switzerland, Depot in Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 4. *Infrared Scan of E (fragmentary Watercolor)* (1918, 1999), Scan Conducted by Myriam Weber, Works on Paper Conservator at the Zentrum Paul Klee. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 5. Paul Klee, *Station L 112, 14 km* (1920, 112), watercolor and pen on paper on cardboard, 12.3 x 21.8 cm, Hermann und Margaret Rupf-Stiftung, Kunstmuseum Bern. Fotocredit: Kunstmuseum Bern.

Figure 6. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: die Gegend zur Reue* (*The Inferner Park: the Area of Repentance*) (1939, 243), Pencil on paper on cardboard, 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 7. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: das Schiff zur zweifelhaftem Rettung* (*The Inferner Park: the Ship of Dubious Salvation*) (1939, 252) Pencil on paper on cardboard, 27 x 43 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 8. Paul Klee, *mir Hering?! (me, Herring?!)*, (1939, 658), pencil on paper on cardboard, 29.5 x 21 cm. Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 9. Paul Klee, *nie mehr jene Speise!* (never again that food!), (1939, 659), pencil on paper on cardboard, 36 x 19 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 10. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: "zur verfrühten Rast"*, 1939, 240 (*The Infernal Park: to the premature Rest*), (1939, 240), Pencil on paper on cardboard, 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 11. Paul Klee, Paul Klee, *d. Inferner Park: "eingangs"*, (*The Inferner Park: on Entering*), (1939, 238), 17.9 x 27 cm, Pencil on paper on cardboard, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 12. Paul Klee, Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: erste Ebene* (*The Inferner Park: First Level*), (1939, 239), 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Pencil on paper on cardboard, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 13. Paul Klee, Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: zur Üppigkeit* (*The Inferner Park: to the Luxuriance*), (1939, 241), 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Pencil on paper on cardboard, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 14. Paul Klee, Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: zur scheinbaren Überbrückung* (*The Inferner Park: at the Apparent Bridging*), (1939, 242), 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Pencil on paper on cardboard, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 15. Paul Klee, Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: die Gegend zur Reue* (*The Infernal Park: the Area of Repentance*), (1939, 243), 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Pencil on paper on cardboard, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 16. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: "die Blüte zur Betäubung"* (*The Inferner Park: the Blossom of Narcosis*), (1939, 244), pencil on paper on cardboard, 29.7 x 20.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 17. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: "Vase N"* (*The Inferner Park: Vase N*), (1939, 246), pencil on paper on cardboard, 29.7 x 20.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 18. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: "zur Entzweiung"* (*The Inferner Park: to the Rupture*), (1939, 247), pencil on paper on cardboard, 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 19. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park: "zu den Winden"* (*The Inferner Park: to the Winds*) (1939, 248), pencil on paper on cardboard, 21.5 x 27 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 20. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park (The Inferner Park)* (1939, 255), watercolor on primed burlap, 39.5 x 70 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 21. Paul Klee, *der Inferner Park* “zur fruchtlosen Umkehr” (*The Inferner Park: to the Fruitless Return*) (1939, 249), pencil on paper on cardboard, 20.9 x 29.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.

Figure 22. Paul Klee, *Mutter und Töchter (Mother and Daughters)* (1939, 315), pencil on paper on cardboard, 29.7 x 20.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Bildarchiv.